

Growth optimization and protein characterization of *Agaricus bisporus* (J.E.Lange) Imbach

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CERTIFICATE

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*Dedicated to my Loving Parents
for their unconditional love,
encouragement, and support*

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Sr. No.	Title	Page No.
1	Acknowledgments	I
2	List of Tables	II
3	List of Figures	III
4	List of Abbreviations	IV
5	Abstract	V
6	Introduction	1
7	Aims and Objectives	12
8	Review of Literature	13
9	Materials and Methods	22
10	Results	29
11	Discussion	62
12	References	69

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Sr. No	Abbreviations	Augmentations
1	BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
2	MSA	Multiple Sequence Alignment
3	NCBI	National Centre for Biotechnology Information
4	UniProt	Universal Protein Resource
5	kDa	Kilo Dalton
6	PDB	Protein Data Bank
7	WHO	World health organization
8	KEGG	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes
9	AbL	<i>Agaricus bisporus</i> laccase
10	UNAG	UDP-N-acetylglucosamine
11	PEP	Phosphoenolpyruvate
12	CADD	Computer-Aided Drug Design
13	vHTS	Virtual High Throughput Screening
14	MEGA	Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis
15	ESPrpt	Easy Sequencing in PostScript
16	MOE	Molecular Operating Environment
17	RMSD	Root Mean Square Deviation

Abstract

The button mushroom, *Agaricus bisporus*, has a long history of cultivation and is currently grown extensively in high-tech facilities. White button mushrooms. One of the most popularly grown mushroom species worldwide is *Agaricus bisporus*. It is favoured by customers who prefer clean eating because of its great nutritional value and variety of health benefits. *Agaricus bisporus* is a species of mushroom that belongs to the family Agaricaceae. *Agaricus bisporus* laccase is a type of protein called laccase that is found in the fruiting body of *Agaricus bisporus* mushroom. FASTA sequence is obtained from UniProtKb with the sequence of 520 amino acids and 50KDa molecular weight. Molecular structure is predicted from SWISS-MODEL by using template 3PXL showing sequence identity of 49.19%. AbL predicted model was validated with ERRAT quality factor of 86.558% and good values of Ramachandran plot with only two residues in disallowed region. VERIFY 3D results shows that 83.20% of the residues have averaged 3D-1D score ≥ 0.1 . At least 80% of the amino acids have scored ≥ 0.1 in the 3D/1D profile. Overall shape of AbL is roughly spherical. Superimposition of AbL with its template *Lentinus tigrinus* (2QT6) is done. AbL has a unique multicopper binding specificity and Glycerol (Pubchem ID GLU 753) was docked to predict AbL structure and it showed its binding. The binding affinity is -6.7(kcal/mol) with RMSD value of 1.381. Total three hydrogen bonds were formed named VAL 79, GLN 105, and TYR 113. In *Agaricus bisporus*, laccase plays an important role in the degradation of certain environmental pollutants particularly aromatic compounds

Introduction

Mushrooms are the fruiting bodies of fungi and constitute a significant food source. Many species of wild or field mushrooms are considered delicacies in some cultures/countries. However, there are numerous mushrooms that may prove toxic if eaten and distinguishing between “edible” and poisonous species is often difficult. In addition, some “edible” species can prove toxic to some humans in certain circumstances which may not be predictable.(White *et al.* 2019)

Mushrooms are fungi with significant nutritional value currently counting around 2000 edible species distributed around the world (Rathore *et al.*, 2019). The most cultivated species include button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*), shiitake mushroom (*Lentinula edodes*), and oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus* spp.). The current global market value of fresh mushroom reached 38 billion US dollars in 2018, and China is the largest mushroom producer within the Asian region, contributing approximately 35 % to the global mushroom market (Elaine and Tan, 2009). Asia countries contribute up to 76 % of mushroom production, followed by Europe (17.2 %) and United States (5.9 %) (Sande *et al.*, 2019).(Mahari *et al.* 2020)

Wild mushrooms are a vital source of income and nutrition for many poor communities and of value to recreational foragers. Literature relating to the edibility of mushroom species continues to expand, driven by an increasing demand for wild mushrooms, a wider interest in foraging, and the study of traditional foods. Although numerous case reports have been published on edible mushrooms, doubt and confusion persist regarding which species are safe and suitable to consume. Case reports often differ, and the evidence supporting the stated properties of mushrooms can be incomplete or ambiguous. The need for greater clarity on edible species is further underlined by increases in mushroom-related poisonings. We propose a system for categorizing mushroom species and assigning a final edibility status. (Li *et al.* 2021)

Mushroom-forming fungi (Agaricomycetes) have the greatest morphological diversity and complexity of any group of fungi. They have radiated into most niches and fulfil diverse roles in the ecosystem, including wood decomposers, pathogens or mycorrhizal mutualists. Despite the importance of mushroom-forming fungi, large-scale patterns of their evolutionary history are poorly known, in part due to the lack of a comprehensive and dated molecular phylogeny. Here, using multigene and genome-based data, we assemble a 5,284-species

phylogenetic tree and infer ages and broad patterns of speciation/extinction and morphological innovation in mushroom-forming fungi. Agaricomycetes started a rapid class-wide radiation in the Jurassic, coinciding with the spread of (sub) tropical coniferous forests and a warming climate. (Varga *et al.* 2019)

Mushrooms with enhanced medicinal properties focus on finding such compounds that could modulate the human body's immune systems. Mushrooms have antimicrobial, antidiabetic, antiviral, hepatoprotective, antitumor, and immunomodulatory properties due to the presence of various bioactive components. β -glucans are the major constituent of the mushroom cell wall and play a significant role in their biological activity. This review described the techniques used in the extraction of the active ingredients from the mushroom. We highlighted the structure of the bioactive polysaccharides present in the mushrooms. Therapeutic applications of different mushrooms were also described. It is interesting to note that mushrooms have the potential sources of many bioactive products that can regulate immunity. Thus, the development of functional medicinal food based on the mushroom is vital for human welfare. (Patel *et al.* 2021)

Mushroom, a fungi kingdom member, has drawn significant interest in medicinal applications due to their anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, cardiovascular-protective, hepatoprotective, and anticancer potentials. It regulated the immune system, and macrophages, T cells, dendritic cells (DC), natural killer (NK) cells, and hematopoietic stem cell activities by phagocytic activity, generating reactive oxygen species, inflammatory mediators, and cytokines production. Mushroom is a rich source of proteins, fibers, and vitamins. It is challenging to distinguish between edible and medicinal mushrooms because many edible mushrooms have therapeutic properties, and many medicinal mushrooms are also edible. Approximately 1.5–5.0 million fungi species are known globally, and among them, a few hundred species have medicinal properties (Patel *et al.* 2021)

Mushroom polysaccharides are a type of bioactive macromolecular which isolated from fruiting bodies, mycelia or fermentation broths of edible or medicinal fungus. Recently, mushroom polysaccharides have attracted a lot of attention for regulating gut microbiota via reducing the levels of pathogens and stimulating the growth of beneficial microorganisms, thus creating new possibilities for their use in nutraceutical and functional foods industries. The current review summarizes the isolation, purification and structural characterization methods of

mushroom polysaccharides, the degradation of mushroom polysaccharides in intestine, the impacts of mushroom polysaccharides on gut microbiota community and short chain fatty acids (SCFAs) productivity, and the beneficial effects of mushroom polysaccharides to host by targeting gut microbiota.(Yin *et al.* 2020)

The use of spent mushroom substrate (SMS) in new cultivation cycles has already been reported due to its economic and environmental viability. When considering the application of the circular economy concept in the production of edible mushrooms, the re-use of the SMS within the same process is highly attractive, because it allows a better use of the biomass and the energy involved in the process and, therefore, tends to improve energy efficiency and resource conservation. However, this alternative generates important challenges, which derive from maintaining the quality standards of the mushrooms produced and, at the same time, not incurring excessive costs that are detrimental to the process itself. In our opinion, the main difficulty of the process in achieving success is regarding the biological and agronomic parameters that involve the production of the mushroom. It is useless to apply SMS in new cycles if the mushroom harvest is impaired and farms become non-viable. (Cunha Zied *et al.* 2020)

To date, 150,000–160,000 mushrooms have been recorded, however, among them, only about 100 species of the prime edible mushrooms are economically cultivated, around 60 commercially cultivated are widely accepted as food sources, and more than 10 produced on an industrial scale in many countries. Most edible mushrooms are rich in nutrients, such as protein, polysaccharides, vitamins, mineral elements as well as various functional factors, all substances are essential for human, as a result, long-term consumption will have a beneficial effect on improvement of human health. Generally speaking, fresh mushrooms contain 85–90% moisture, and the mentioned nutritional values is recognized as components in dried individuals.(Gong *et al.* 2020)

Even though mushrooms are often considered to be a vegetable, they actually belong to the fungal kingdom. There are >2000 species of mushrooms in nature, ≥ 25 of which are widely accepted as functional foods for human consumption and commercially cultivated. Overall, mushrooms have been reported to have anticancer capabilities and protective effects against tumor development and laboratory studies have revealed these anticarcinogenic effects vary

according to different types of mushrooms such as shiitake, maitake, and *Agaricus bisporus* (button mushroom). Several epidemiological observational studies have also reported an inverse association between mushroom consumption and cancer risk. However, several other epidemiological studies that have examined the effects of mushroom intake on the risk of cancer have yielded nonsignificant associations. (Ba *et al.* 2021)

Mushrooms belong to phylum basidiomycetes which are huge and amazingly diverse group that along with the ascomycetes, constitute the kingdom *Dikarya*, collectively referred to as the “higher fungi” (Shipley *et al.*, 2016). They have a distinctive body that be can be epigeous or hypogeous, large enough that they are visible to the naked eye and can be picked by hand. Majority of the edible mushroom species belong to the class *Agaricomycetes* that produces basidiocarps such as gilled mushrooms, puffballs, bracket, coral, jelly and crust fungi (Hibbett, 2006). There are about 12,000 species of such mushrooms available worldwide. Of these, 2000 species are considered edible and 35 are commercially cultivated throughout the world (Rathore, Prasad, & Sharma, 2017). Further, mushrooms are known to possess extensive enzyme complexes that enable them to flourish successfully on lignocellulosic substrates containing lignin, celluloses, hemicelluloses and pectin (Rathore *et al.* 2019)

In the developed world communicable diseases account for maximum proportion of ailments nowadays. Global morbidity and even mortality are sometimes associated with common pathogens. Several severe infections and complications occur in the present context such as acute gastroenteritis (AGE), colitis, bloodstream infection, meningitis, joint infection, strep throat, urinary tract infections (UTIs), bacterial food poisoning, bacterial cellulitis and vaginosis, gonorrhea, chlamydia, syphilis, respiratory tract infection etc. The extensive use of antibiotics and fungicides to protect against infections by pathogens contributed immensely to many medical achievements. On the downside of these measures a high number of multi-drug resistant pathogens has also emerged of late(Pandey *et al.* 2020)

Dramatic increases in the speed and quality of imaging, segmentation and reconstruction in electron microscopy now allow large-scale, dense connectomic studies of nervous systems. Such studies can reveal the chemical synapses between all neurons, generating a complete connectivity map. Connectomics is particularly useful in generating biological insights when applied to an ensemble of neurons with interesting behavioral functions that have already been

extensively studied experimentally. Knowing the effects on behavior and physiology of perturbing individual cell types that can also be unambiguously identified in the connectome is of considerable value. Here, we present a connectomic analysis of one such neuronal ensemble, the mushroom body (MB) of an adult *Drosophila melanogaster*.(Li *et al.* 2020)

Mushroom substrate is a mushroom growing media that consists of several organic materials such as sawdust and rice bran. The substrate media can no longer be used and needs to be disposed of upon completion of several cycles of mushroom harvesting. The production of mushrooms in Malaysia was estimated to be 24 ton day⁻¹. This led to generation up to 5 kg of by-product (i.e. spent mushroom substrate (SMS)) from 1 kg of mushroom product. Therefore, approximately 120 metric tons of SMS have been produced daily by the mushroom industry.(Lam *et al.* 2019)

Lignocellulosic biomass with inherent recalcitrance embedded in the structural components has valuable and sustainable energy sources to produce environmentally friendly energy, and the use of that energy plays a crucial role in sustainable development strategies. Lignocellulosic biomass is considered a good source of renewable feedstocks and contains high fermentable sugars. However, the lignocellulosic-based feedstock is a recalcitrant material that requires intensive labor and high capital cost for processing. Biodegradation of the lignocellulosic materials is associated with harsh processing conditions such as extreme pH and temperature, high salinity, metal ions, and organic solvents; therefore, laccases can function in these harsh conditions are in increasing demand. Incorporating laccases in the bioconversion of lignocellulosic biomass is very attractive and advantageous due to the depolymerization of lignin under a milder and cleaner conditions without damaging the cellulose. These ligninolytic enzymes are considered ecofriendly alternatives for biodelignifying natural wastes offering economic benefits through decreasing lignocellulosic biowastes accumulation. Bacteria can effectively degrade lignocellulose.(Gałązka *et al.* 2023)

Lignocellulosic biomass is composed of three major biopolymers: cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. Analytical tools capable of quickly detecting both glycan and lignin deconstruction are needed to support the development and characterization of efficient enzymes/enzyme cocktails. Previously we have described nanostructure-initiator mass spectrometry-based assays for the analysis of glycosyl hydrolase and most recently an assay for

lignin modifying enzymes. Here we integrate these two assays into a single multiplexed assay against both classes of enzymes and use it to characterize crude commercial enzyme mixtures. Application of our multiplexed platform based on nanostructure-initiator mass spectrometry enabled us to characterize crude mixtures of laccase enzymes from fungi *Agaricus bisporus* (*Ab*) and *Myceliophthora thermophila* (*Mt*) revealing activity on both carbohydrate and aromatic substrates. Using time-series analysis we determined that crude laccase from *Ab* has the higher GH activity and that laccase from *Mt* has the higher activity against our lignin model compound. Inhibitor studies showed a significant reduction in *Mt* GH activity under low oxygen conditions and increased activities in the presence of vanillin (common GH inhibitor). Ultimately, this assay can help to discover mixtures of enzymes that could be incorporated into biomass pretreatments to deconstruct diverse components of lignocellulosic biomass.(Ghorai 2022)

There is a growing need to find renewable and eco-friendly sources of energy. Lignocellulosic biomass has great potential to create sustainable drop-in replacements for conventional petroleum-based fuels. It is composed of three major biopolymers: cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin and therefore maximal breakdown will require efficient deconstruction of both the glycans via glycosyl hydrolases (GHs) and lignin by lignin modifying enzymes (LMEs). It is desirable to develop chemically resolved assays that are suitable for simultaneously characterizing both GH and LME activities because lignin products can impede enzymatic saccharification through nonproductive binding interactions with carbohydrate-active enzymes. Finding enzymes/enzyme cocktails which can cleave both carbohydrate and phenolic bonds has great potential to help prevent this deactivation and aid in both lignin and glycan deconstruction towards the development of bioproducts.(Giannakopoulou *et al.*)

Laccases are a class of lignin-active enzymes which catalyze single-electron oxidations of aromatic substrates by using oxygen as a terminal electron acceptor. When coupled with a mediator such as 2,2'-azinobis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonate) (ABTS), laccases can oxidize nonphenolic substrates as well, making them a target enzyme for lignin deconstruction. To our knowledge no specific analytical methods have been developed to simultaneously characterize the breakdown product distribution of lignin and cellulose model compounds. Here, we report the integration of existing NIMS assays using cellobiose probes with the recently reported phenolic β -aryl ether probe to simultaneously assay activities against lignin and glycan model compounds.

We selected the β -aryl ether bond for our studies because it is the most common linkage in lignin.

Epigallocatechin-3-O-gallate (EGCG), one of the most abundant monomeric catechin compounds in green tea, was oxidized to EGCG dimers through radical oxidative reaction using laccase, a member of the tea polyphenol oxidase family. Electrospray ionization tandem LC-MS (ESI-LC/MS) was applied for the characterization of the dimers, including theacitrin, dehydrotheasinensin, and theasinensin, which were produced by the radical oxidative reaction. Chemical structures of the EGCG dimer were identified using LC/MS/MS and fragmentation patterns of EGCG dimer. The dimers were isomerized by heat treatment at 80°C after oxidation step to mimic heat treatment and drying in the last step of leaf fermentation. As a result of the heat treatment, theasinensin A (TSA) was formed as a major dimer product. After the two steps of Sephadex LH-20 and C18 column chromatography, 27.6 mg of purified TSA was obtained from 485.4 mg of dried reaction mixture. Biological effect of TSA as antioxidant and anti-aging effects were investigated. (Giannakopoulou *et al.* 2022)

Postharvest browning in white button mushroom is a major limiting factor determining the quality and marketability of mushrooms. In the present study, 361 hybrids were developed using non-fertile isolates from eleven button mushroom strains. A total of forty one browning tolerant hybrids were selected and evaluated for the yield. Five of these were evaluated on large scale in commercial units and two have been finally selected on the basis of higher yield than the strains used by the commercial units. The selected five hybrids showed very low level of enzymes responsible for browning i.e., laccase, polyphenol oxidases and tyrosinase. The hybrids were characterized using SSR, IRAP and ReMAP markers and distinguishing bands for hybrids could be identified. The developed hybrids will address postharvest browning problems of button mushroom industry. (GUGALIA)

Marine organisms, especially macroalgae, constitute a renowned source of bioactive compounds. Among marine macroalgae, *Ulva* species, green seaweeds belonging to the order Ulvales (Chlorophyta), have recently attracted scientific interest. Specifically, *Ulva intestinalis*, a bright grass-green seaweed, rich in polysaccharides, proteins, minerals, and other bioactive substances, such as phenolics has gained increasing attention over the last years. These species

produce a wide variety of secondary metabolites with a broad array of bioactivities, including antitumoral, antiviral, antifungal, antibacterial, antiaging, cytotoxic and antiproliferative activity. For example, a protein fraction from *Ulva intestinalis* induced a remarkable increase in collagen and hyaluronic acid production per cell and reduced cell proliferation without increasing cell mortality. Although these species are yet much underexploited, the remarkable potential arising from their exploitation approves their compelling scientific interest, especially in the pharmaceutical and food industries.(Hidalgo *et al.* 2023)

The blue multicopper oxidase enzyme laccase (EC 1.10.3.2) has the ability to catalyze the oxidation process of phenolic and non-phenolic aromatic substrates while also reducing molecular oxygen to water. Using molecular oxygen as an electron acceptor, laccase oxidizes its substrates by an electron transfer mechanism that generates unstable free radical intermediates and causes non-enzymatic reactions that break down substrate molecules . Laccase substrate specificity differs from one organism to another, and in the presence of adequate redox mediators, the range of laccase oxidizable substrates can be greatly extended. Laccase is a glycosylated monomer with a molecular mass ranging from 54 to 97 kDa, relying on the source species. Numerous environmental pollutants, such as bisphenol A (BPA), may be successfully broken down and mineralized by fungi using their laccases. Laccase belongs to the polyphenol oxidases family, and its active site contains four copper atoms from types T₁, T₂, and T₃.(Iqhrammullah *et al.* 2023)

Laccase enzymes, multi-copper oxidases found in plants, insects, fungi, and bacteria, have inspired biobased strategies for the treatment of recalcitrant compounds due to their ability to oxidatively degrade lignin using molecular oxygen as a terminal electron acceptor. Bacterial laccases tend to have a higher thermotolerance and a wider pH range, while fungal laccases tend to have higher redox potentials (~0.5–0.8 V vs NHE). While they exhibit broad substrate specificity, the performance of laccase with respect to contaminant transformation is limited by its oxidation potential. (Iqhrammullah *et al.* 2023)

In the current scenario 64 %, 26 %, and 10 % ethanol is produced from maize, sugarcane, and wheat flour or other grain sources respectively by the traditional fermentation process. In 2020, the United States of America was the leading country to produce the highest (13.8 billion

gallons) amount of ethanol; Brazil was the second-largest alcohol producer (7.9 billion gallons), while 0.88 and 0.48 billion gallons were produced by China and India respectively. Recently it was estimated; globally ethanol generation will increase up to 37 billion gallons by 2029. As a result, to expect the production of such a huge amount of alcohol will be needed of >25 % and 14 % of global sugarcane and maize production respectively (Agricultural outlook OECD/FAO, 2020). Such a diversion and misuse of food grains to generate alcohol are considered as one of the main reasons to raise food prices all over the world. On the other hand, corn and many other grains are also used as feedstock for poultry and in livestock management as a part of the food based economy.(Jayakumar *et al.* 2023)

Global threat from emerging contaminants to human health has pushed researchers to develop pollutant removal technologies including those based on biocatalytic degradation. Laccase, a multicopper enzyme, is reported for its applicability in treating wastewater and industrial effluent by catalyzing reduction of O₂ to H₂O in the presence of substrates (phenolic or non-phenolic compounds). Scientific papers have discussed the ability of this enzyme to breakdown hazardous contaminants ranging from azo dyes, antibiotics, and up to hormones. Nonetheless, the cost production of this enzyme is high, hence the importance of the immobilization into solid supports. Polymers are considered suitable for the immobilization because they are easy for modification and have adjustable characteristics. This review discusses the immobilization of laccase into polymers via various techniques (adsorption, cross-linking, covalent binding, encapsulation, and entrapment) and its implications on the pollutant removal performance. In addition, bibliometric analysis is performed and summarized the advantages and disadvantages of each immobilization technique.(Johnnie *et al.*)

Increasing anthropogenic activities have contributed to the massive pollutants discharge into environment ascribed to insufficient wastewater infrastructure and limited options for disposal methods. These conditions particularly become more challenging in the face of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, where organic waste is discharged to rivers and water bodies without proper treatment. Excessive and inefficient use of cleaning and sanitizing agents during the pandemic has alarmed researchers regarding their deleterious impact on environment. On daily basis, humans and other organisms are threatened by the presence of

emerging contaminants which include pharmaceuticals (antibiotics, hormones, etc.), pesticides and herbicides, plastic additives, non-halogenated compounds, and so on. Non-nutritive sweetener, a sugar substitute used in various food products, is also considered an emerging contaminant owing to its resistance and stability in aquatic environments.(Juan *et al.* 2022)

One-dimensional Ni/Au/PPy-COOH nanowires with multiple segments were synthesized in this study. Smooth surfaces and magnetic properties of nanowires were investigated by scanning transmission electron microscopy (SEM), Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), and Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) techniques. The nanowires were used to modify the screen-printed electrode surface and as a micro-environment for *Trametes versicolor* laccase. The ability of this enzyme biosensor to detect dopamine change in human biological samples was demonstrated by a wide linear range (0.01–50 μM) and a low LOD (2.265 nM). In addition, the biosensor exhibited excellent selectivity allowing the detection of dopamine in the presence of ascorbic acid, uric acid, L-Cys, serotonin, and glucose, with high sensitivity of reduction currents obtained at -0.2 V (*vs.* Ag/AgCl). The proposed biosensor allowed the detection of dopamine in commercial serum and artificial urine with recovery values close to 100 %. It also demonstrated reproducibility, reusability, and long-term storage stability. The sensitivity, K_m^{app} , and I_{max} values of the biosensor were determined as 2.05 μM and 1.03 μA , respectively. The LAC-Ni/Au/PPy-COOH/NAF/SPE biosensor is a reliable design for detecting dopamine with a wide linear range.(Kaur *et al.* 2022)

Dopamine (DA), 3,4-dihydroxyphenethylamine, is a catecholamine neurotransmitter in the transmission between cells and is found in the human body. Dopamine is a primary amine belonging to the biogenic amine class and plays a significant role in the functioning of the central nervous, renal, hormonal, cardiovascular, and endocrine systems. High levels of dopamine in the body are an indicator of diseases such as rapid heart rates, hypertension, and heart failure. While it is thought that low dopamine levels may cause neurological disorders such as Parkinson's disease, Schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease, stress, and depression (the dopamine level in a healthy individual is in the range of 0.01–0.1 μM). Dopamine measurement is usually performed using analytical techniques such as liquid chromatography and capillary electrophoresis. Despite their low detection limits, these techniques have significant limitations, such as large equipment

requirements, long analysis times, and cause organic waste. For these reasons, it is pivotal to develop biosensors for faster and more convenient detection of dopamine as a biomarker. The co-existence of small molecules such as ascorbic acid and uric acid in the blood, urine, and extracellular fluids causes high interference at similar potentials on bare electrodes during the detection of dopamine.(Kumar *et al.* 2022)

A multicopper oxidase, laccases catalyze the four-electron reduction of the substrate with the use of molecular oxygen. Laccases are abundant in nature and can be found in virtually every form of life on the planet. Generally speaking, laccases are classified into three types: blue, white, and yellow. Plant, bacterial and fungal laccases all have the same trinuclear copper site for substrate reduction. Non-phenolic as well as phenolic molecules are both capable of being catalyzed by this enzyme. Laccases are used in a wide range of industries that make use of phenolic chemicals. Laccases have been the subject of recent research because of their unique features. Laccase, its sources, manufacture, purification, and applications in many sectors are discussed in length in this review.(Kyomuhimbo & Brink 2023)

The search for ecologically friendly technologies has increased interest in using enzymes to replace conventional non-biological methods, which are increasingly becoming popular. Laccases (benzenediol: oxygen oxidoreductases; EC 1.10.3.2) have received the most attention in recent decades when comparing the many oxidant enzymes currently exist. In nature, laccases are multicopper oxidases that may be found in abundance. They catalyze the one-electron oxidation of phenolic compounds, resulting in the simultaneous reduction of oxygen to water in the presence of oxygen.(Leutbecher *et al.* 2009)

Enzymes are utilized in industrial processes to make them cleaner and more effective, as well as to support the idea of sustainable development. Enzymatic reactions have a number of advantages over conventional chemical processes, which leads to improved resource utilization and reducing waste in product development. In this aspect, laccases (EC.1.10.3.2) are metals containing mononuclear enzymes which can oxidize a wide range of phenols, aromatic amines, and heterocyclic compounds with low redox potential properties. According to the UniProtKB database search results for "laccase," the enzyme is identified in 1026 bacteria, 6258 eukaryotes, and 16 halobacteria (archaea), with sequence sizes ranging from 220 to 800 amino acids. As a

result, it is reasonable to expect that the incredible number of enzymes generated by various species will have a wide variety of uses. (Leutbecher *et al.* 2009)

Green chemistry elements should deal with enzymatic chemical reactions that are efficient or have a low environmental impact. Laccase is a readily available multicopper oxidase that has been extensively studied for a long time. In reviewing recent trends in laccase research, the authors selected themes that have not yet been evaluated, targeting open-access journals. From a chemical viewpoint, decomposition reactions (such as oxidation of substrates, toxic substances, pigments, and biomass materials), organic synthesis reactions, composite catalytic activities of oxygen reduction reactions, biosensors, batteries, biological fields, fermentation, culture, gene association, and antifungal activity.(Li *et al.* 2022)

The growing demand for biofuels production using vegetable oils leads to a continuous increase of the amount of glycerol, the secondary product of the biodiesel industry, available on the market. Even though efficient large-scale recovery and valorization methods of this low-cost byproduct are still being developed, there is an extensive research focusing on this topic. Since the volumetric biodiesel to glycerol ratio is 10:1, the continuously increasing production of this biofuel was estimated to generate globally 7.66 million tons glycerol in 2020 and, therefore, a consistent polyol surplus on the market, with the consequent need of novel sustainable technologies for its conversion in value-added products. Glycerol (1,2,3-propanetriol) is an important starting material for the synthesis of many important chemical compounds by various catalytic routes such as pyrolysis, reforming, hydrogenation, oxidation, or esterification, subject of several biorefinery strategies.(Li *et al.* 2022)

Plant phenolic compounds demonstrate bioactive properties *in vitro* and/or *in vivo*, which creates demand for their precise determination in life sciences and industry. Measuring the concentration of individual phenolic compounds is a complex task, since approximately 9000 plant phenolic substances have been identified so far. The determination of the total phenolic content (TPC) is less laborious and is used for the qualimetric evaluation of complex multicomponent samples in routine analyses. Biosensors based on phenol oxidases (POs) have been proposed as alternative analytical devices for detecting phenolic compounds; however, their effectiveness in the analysis of food and vegetal matrices has not been addressed in detail. This

review describes catalytic properties of laccase and tyrosinase and reports on the enzymatic and bienzymatic sensors based on laccase and tyrosinase for estimating the total phenolic index (TPI) in food-related samples (FRSs). The review presents the classification of biosensors, POs immobilization, the functions of nanomaterials, the biosensing catalytic cycle, interference, validation, and some other aspects related to TPI assessment. Nanomaterials are involved in the processes of immobilization, electron transfer, signal formation, and amplification, and they improve the performance of PO-based biosensors. Possible strategies for reducing interference in PO-based biosensors are discussed, namely the removal of ascorbic acid and the use of highly purified enzymes. (Lim & Mohamad 2022)

Laccase is a key enzyme in the fungal 1,8-dihydroxynaphthalene(DHN) melanin biosynthesis pathway, which is a potential target for the control of pathogenic fungi. In our previous work, **a2** was found with higher inhibition activity against laccase and antifungal activity than laccase inhibitor PMDD-5Y. The introduction of hydrogen-bonded receptors in amino part was found to be beneficial in improving laccase inhibitory activity by target-based-biological rational design. In this work, the hydrogen-bonded receptors morpholine and piperazine were introduced for structure optimization to enhancing biological activity. Enzyme activity tests indicated that all target compounds had inhibitory activity against laccase, and some compounds exhibited better activity against laccase than **a2**, it was further verified the introduction of hydrogen-bonded receptors in the amino portion could enhance the laccase inhibitory activity of target compounds. Most compounds showed excellent antifungal activities *in vitro*. (Lin *et al.* 2023)

Regarding inorganic contaminants, Raj *et al.* (2011) highlighted the capacity of some fungi to accumulate high concentrations of metals (e.g., Pb) in their fruiting bodies. Furthermore, Kulshreshtha (2018) and García-Delgado *et al.* (2013) reported that SMS can act as metal adsorbent due to the presence of fungal mycelia. Nevertheless, there is still insufficient knowledge on the suitability of SMS to reduce bioavailable metal concentrations in soil. In any case, mycoremediation is widely recognized as a bioremediation strategy of great potential, particularly for soils contaminated with recalcitrant organic compounds (Kulshreshtha *et al.*,

2014; Singh, 2006). Importantly, the use of SMS for mycoremediation purposes (an example of waste valorisation) is in accordance with the circular economy paradigm.(Liu *et al.* 2022).

Aims and Objectives

1. Growth optimization and cultivation of *Agaricus bisporus* (white button mushroom) on cheaper substrate.
2. Structure prediction, validation, and comparative analysis of *A. bisporus* Laccase (AbL) predicted model.
3. Docking of Glycerol (GLU) in AbL predicted model to highlight the interactions between enzyme and ligand.

Review of literature

Chapter No. 2

(Akinyemi et al., 2020)The laccase enzymes of *Agaricus bisporus* and *Trametes versicolor* were successfully covalently co-immobilized on poly(glycidyl methacrylate) microspheres. The enzyme load reached after the co-immobilization of both enzymes was 6.75 U g^{-1} carrier. The resulting biocatalyst showed the combined properties of both immobilized enzymes, increasing their optimum pH and temperature ranges. The storage and operational stabilities were also improved after co-immobilization. In the presence of a mediator (ABTS), the organophosphate pesticide diazinon was 100% biodegraded after 48 h of reaction with 0.2 U/mL of co-immobilized enzymes (at the two maximum activity pH values: 2.0 and 3.0). In the absence of a mediator, the degradation percentages were above 88%. Data showed that, compared with single enzymatic immobilization, the co-immobilization of the two laccases is an easy, efficient, and low cost alternative to expanding the range of work of the biocatalyst, thereby improving the stability and some biochemical properties to generate a powerful alternative for pesticide degradation in a wide range of conditions.

(Akitsu & Nakane, 2020)The search for seeking novel immobilized enzyme carriers is a hot topic in the field of enzyme engineering. As a kind of common office consumable, magnetic printing toner has been terribly wasted, leading to potential harm to the environment. We try to use printing toner as carrier for enzyme immobilization to realize waste reuse. In this paper, the laccase extracted from *Agaricus bisporus* was successfully immobilized on chitosan coated magnetic printing toner by glutaraldehyde linking. The use of printing toner is proved to be feasible. The results show that the optimal temperature of immobilized laccase is $40 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the optimal pH is 3.0. Compared with free laccase, the optimal temperature and optimal pH have been obviously changed after immobilization. And the pH tolerance has been significantly improved, which can remain 53% activity after 5 cycles. Because of the use of magnetic printing toner, it is more convenient to recycle the immobilized enzyme. In this study, printing toner was used as carrier for the immobilization of enzyme and the discarded printing toner recycling was realized.

(Akram et al., 2020)As a kind of biofunctional material, laccases with superior intrinsic optical property are garnering substantial interest in enzyme-based optical biosensing due to their great potential use in the field of food, environment and industry. However, it is still unclear as to the variation mechanism of enzyme intrinsic optical property,

Chapter No. 2

and thus limits the application. For exploring the variation mechanism, the current study presents the optical characterization of *Agaricus bisporus* laccase and focus on real-time monitoring polymerics formation, both theoretically and experimentally, in order to lay a foundation for laccase-based optical biosensing application. According to bioinformatics analysis, the results show that the target laccase has conserved copper binding site, and the related amino acid residues possibly have positive effect on the florescence of Typ in this region. On the basis of experimental characterization, the results show that the enzyme displays an obvious absorption peak at approximately 400 nm (optimal pH 7.0), and the strongest fluorescence of enzyme centers at around the excitation wavelength of 280 nm and emission wavelength of 340 nm (optimal pH 6.0); organic ethanol serves as an active enhancer toward the absorbance of enzyme.

(AKTAŞ UYGUN & EVLİ 2020)Direct electrochemistry of oxidoreductase on electrode plays critical roles in the development of enzymatic biosensing and biofuel cells. Herein, a free-standing edge-rich graphene (ERG) film in-situ fabricated on a porous and conductive Si₃N₄ nanowires template with hydrophobic surface was directly used as a self-supporting electrode for site-directed capture of laccase from *Agaricus bisporus*. The ERG film possessed abundant edge-rich active sites, high conductivity, and especially hydrophobic surface, which realized the direct electron transfer of the immobilized laccase and its bioelectrocatalysis towards the O₂ reduction. With the comprehensive comparison to hydrophilic ERG, we found that the interfacial hydrophobicity played an important role for the orientated immobilization of laccase. Thereafter a faster electron transfer kinetic (1.32 vs. 0.74 s⁻¹) and a higher bioelectrocatalytic activity towards O₂ with over 10 times' enhancement in reductive current were achieved. This is probably because the hydrophobic region of laccase tends to specifically interact with the hydrophobic surface, allowing the site-directed capture of laccase on the hydrophobic ERG electrode. With an emphasis of the interfacial hydrophobicity effect, these results would not only contribute to an in-depth understanding of the nano-bio interface electron transfer, but also provide a new insight to design high-efficient bioelectrodes for biosensors and biofuel cells applications.

(AKTAŞ UYGUN & EVLİ)A homogeneous monomeric laccase (ASL) from *Agaricus sinodeliciosus*, with a molecular mass of 65 kDa, was isolated using ion-exchange chromatography (CM-cellulose and Q-Sepharose) and gel-filtration chromatography (Superdex 75). This laccase exhibited maximum activity at 50 °C and pH 5.0. Hg²⁺ and Cd²⁺ significantly inhibited its activity. The laccase displayed a K_m value of

Chapter No. 2

0.9 mM toward 2,2'-azinobis-(3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulfonate) (ABTS). In addition to ABTS, ASL exhibited higher affinity toward o-toluidine and benzidine than other substrates. ASL is able to decolorize malachite green and Eriochrome black T.

(Annunziata, 2021) Biomass derived from green marine macroalgae *Ulva* sp. is considered a rich source of bioactive compounds. In the present study, we demonstrate the increased bioactivity of a phenolic-rich extract derived from green marine macroalgae *Ulva intestinalis* after its treatment with fungal laccases from *Trametes versicolor* and *Agaricus bisporus*. The phenolic composition of the extract, before and after its enzymatic treatment, was determined through several analytical methods. Furthermore, the antioxidant, enzyme-inhibitory, antimicrobial and cytotoxic activity of enzymatically modified and non-modified extracts was comparatively investigated. Depending on the laccase used, the enzyme-modified extracts exhibited different phenolic content and enhanced bioactivities compared to the non-treated ones. The enzymatically modified extracts presented enhanced antimicrobial, anti-lipoxygenase and anti-collagenase activities, and mild cytotoxicity. These results indicate that the proposed biocatalytic process could be applied to produce green macroalgal natural extracts with enhanced bioactivities paving the way for their implementation in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmeceutical industries.

(Antón-Herrero et al., 2021) Laccases show multiple biotechnological application and different fungal groups have been widely reported as laccase producers. The main aim of our research it was to perform on-plate screening for laccase production among different macro and micromycetes, while optimising the screening protocol in the presence of different guaiacol concentrations. From our collection were taken into account filamentous fungi belonging to the following species: *Aspergillus clavatus*, *A. aculeatus*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Neurospora crassa*, *Trichoderma* sp., *Penicillium digitatum*. Among the macromycetes were tested *Laetiporus sulphureus*, *Ganoderma lucidum*, *Agaricus bisporus* and *Pleurotus ostreatus*. The screening was performed on PDA added with guaiacol. The positive microorganisms belong to two strains of *Trichoderma* spp. isolated from soils, one variety of *P. ostreatus* and two of *A. bisporus* originating from supermarket wastes. In the case of *P. ostreatus*, the use of guaiacol higher than 0.1% has inhibited the fungal growth, as well as the halo-formation. In the case of *Trichoderma* spp. strains the use of guaiacol above 0.1% and till 1% didn't lead to any halo formation, while the mycelial growth was not inhibited; relevant halos were registered for the concentrations of 0.01% and 0.025%, when the maximum was reached after 6-7 cultivation days.

Chapter No. 2

(Ariaeenejad et al., 2021)Co-immobilization of several enzymes on the same matrix might enhance the efficiency of bioremediation of water resources. In pursuit of this objective, laccase and tyrosinase are especially important due to their reliance on molecular oxygen during the oxidation of various compounds. Accordingly, in this research, the substrate spectra of a laccase (obtained from *Neurospora crassa*) and a tyrosinase (obtained from *Agaricus bisporus*) were studied through analysis of their reactions with different diazo derivatives of phenol, catechol, guaiacol, and aniline, which were made from an identical molecular structure. The results were explained in view of the influential parameters on the substrate selectivity of each enzyme. The outcome of this research indicates that co-immobilization of laccase with a tyrosinase possibly expands the spectrum of the target pollutants, however, it does not guarantee the efficacy of the system against aniline derivatives.

(Bansal & Sevda, 2022)Laccase treatment of phenolic compounds found in lignocellulosic hydrolysates is an alternative to reduce the growth inhibitory effect of these compounds on fermenting microorganisms. In order to determine the main factors that affect the efficiency of this biocatalytic approach, laccase oxidation of individual and mixtures of phenolic compounds was evaluated. Additionally, the effect of phenolic compounds on *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cell physiology and their effect on yeast membrane liposome models were evaluated. *Trametes versicolor* laccase showed complete oxidation of six phenolic compounds, while *Agaricus bisporus* laccase showed oxidation percentages ranging between 30–100%. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) analyses suggested that compounds such as syringic acid, catechol and gallic acid were not completely polymerised after laccase treatment, which could explain the increase of negative effects observed when they were added to *S. cerevisiae* cultures. Ferulic acid and vanillin oxidation led to a 6.4 and 6.5-fold increase in ethanol production, respectively, compared with the untreated cultures. In phenolic mixtures, chemical interactions between phenolic compounds led to biotransformation of these compounds since different by-products were observed in HPLC chromatograms.

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(Cao et al., 2022)Two laccase isoenzymes (LacA and LacB) were isolated from a novel *Trichoderma harzianum* S7113 isolate employing ammonium sulfate precipitation, Sephadex G100, and DEAE Sepharose ion exchange chromatography. The molecular weights

Chapter No. 2

of the purified LacA and LacB laccases were estimated to be 63 and 48 kDa, respectively. The two isoenzymes had their optimum activities at the same temperature (50 °C), but at slightly different pH values (pH 3.0 for LacA and pH 2.5 for LacB). LacA and LacB had the same thermal stability at 40 °C and pH stability at pH 9.0. The two isoenzymes also showed a high level of specific activity toward ABTS, where the K_m values of LacA and LacB were 0.100 and 0.065 mM, whereas their V_{max} values were 0.603 and 0.182 $\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$, respectively. LacA and LacB catalytic activity was stimulated by Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , K^+ , and Ni^{2+} , whereas it was inhibited by Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} , β -mercaptoethanol, EDTA, and SDS, and completely inhibited by sodium azide. Our findings indicate that purified laccase has a promising capacity for bisphenol A (BPA) bioremediation across a broad pH range. This finding opens up new opportunities for the commercialization of this technique in a variety of biotechnology-based applications, particularly for removing endocrine chemicals from the environment.

(Cardullo et al., 2022) It was partially purified from mushroom compost with cheap and simple purification methods. Partially purified laccase was immobilized onto Amberlite XAD-7 resin. Immobilization conditions and textile dye (Direct Green B) decolorization of immobilized enzyme were examined. Laccase was partially purified from mushroom compost with 3.22 purification fold. Immobilization time for laccase was 30 minutes with 97% efficiency. The immobilization yield based on the activity was calculated by about 90%. The immobilization yield was calculated as nearly 95% based on the measurement of protein amount at each stage. Immobilized enzyme preserved its initial activity with an 84% rate even after its tenth use. The free enzyme lost its activity immediately when it was incubated with the dye solution under its optimal conditions (pH 3.0 and 65°C). On the contrary, the immobilized enzyme maintained its initial activity with a 53% rate when incubated with dye solution under its optimal conditions (pH 3.5 and 65°C).

(Cen et al., 2022) *Agaricus bisporus* growth alters the lignocellulosic composition and structure of compost. However, it is difficult to differentiate the enzyme activities of *A. bisporus* mycelia from the wider microbial community owing to the complication of completely separating the mycelia from compost cultures. Macrogenomics analysis was employed in this study to examine the fermentation substrate of *A. bisporus* before and after mycelial growth, and the molecular mechanism of substrate utilization by *A. bisporus* mycelia was elucidated from the perspective of microbial communities and CAZymes in the substrate. The results showed that the relative abundance of *A.*

Chapter No. 2

bisporus mycelia increased by 77.57-fold after mycelial colonization, the laccase content was significantly increased and the lignin content was significantly decreased. Analysis of the CAZymes showed that AA10 family was extremely differentiated. Laccase-producing strains associated with AA10 family were mostly bacteria belonging to *Thermobifida* and *Thermostaphylospora*, suggesting that these bacteria may play a synergistic role in lignin decomposition along with *A. bisporus* mycelia. These findings provide preliminary evidence for the molecular mechanism of compost utilization by *A. bisporus* mycelia and offer a reference for the development and utilization of strains related to lignocellulose degradation.

(Chang et al., 2022) This study investigated the use of nanozeolites as support for laccases from *P. ostreatus* (LPO), *Aspergillus* sp (LAsp) and *A. bisporus* (LAB) immobilization applied to 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-N-oxyl (TEMPO) mediated glycerol oxidation. Selected complexes led to up to 5% glycerol conversion, and interestingly, up to 100% selectivity to glyceraldehyde after 48 h. Free enzymes led to significantly higher yields (up to 82%) but lacked selectivity when tested under the same conditions. These findings suggest that laccases immobilized into nanozeolites are promising catalysts for the selective oxidation of glycerol. With the aim to understand the different behavior of free or immobilized enzymes, electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy was applied. A significant shift of the T2 parallel copper hyperfine coupling constant was observed. This suggested a perturbation on the catalytic site after immobilization due to pH variation of the enzymatic microenvironments, thus influencing performance of laccase immobilized on nanozeolites.

(Chares Subash & Maheshwari, 2022) Microorganisms strongly influence and are required to generate the selective substrate that provides nutrients and support for fungal growth, and ultimately to induce mushroom fructification under controlled environmental conditions. The bacterial diversity in compost and casing increased throughout the crop cycle boosted by the connection of both substrates. As reflected by the PLFAs, the total living bacterial biomass appears to be negatively correlated with the mycelium of the crop. *Agaricus bisporus* was the dominant fungal species in colonized substrates, displacing the pre-eminent Ascomycota, accompanied by a sustained increase in laccase activity, which is considered to be a major product of protein synthesis during the mycelial growth of champignon. From phase II onwards, the metabolic machinery of the fungal crop degrades lignin and

Chapter No. 2

carbohydrates in compost, while these components are hardly degraded in casing, which reflects the minor role of the casing for nourishing the crop.

(Chen et al., 2022)Tyrosinase exhibits monophenol monooxygenase (EC 1.14.18.1) and o-diphenol: oxygen-oxidoreductase (EC1.10.3.1) activities. Laccase (EC 1.10.3.2) exhibits the p-diphenol:oxygen-oxidoreductase activity. Both the enzymes are grouped under oxidoreductases, which are present in most plants, fungi, bacteria, archaea, lichens and mammals [1,2,3]. Tyrosinase catalyzes the oxidation of L-tyrosine into melanin via dopaquinone and L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-DOPA); L-DOPA is administered in the treatment of Parkinson's disease [4]. Laccase oxidizes a variety of phenols, non-phenolic substrates, and aromatic compounds and is the most suitable enzyme for industrial applications, such as oxidation of xenobiotic compounds and in the pulp and paper industry [5, 6]. In terms of oxidation activity, the main difference between laccase and tyrosinase is their substrate specificity. While laccase is capable of oxidizing syringaldazine and other phenolics as well as non-phenolic substrates, tyrosinase can oxidize only L-tyrosine. In addition, tyrosinase exhibits ceresolase activity, while laccase does not.

(Choi et al., 2022)The oxidation of oleuropein and 3-hydroxytyrosol by oxidases laccase, tyrosinase, and peroxidase has been studied. The use of a spectrophotometric method and another spectrophotometric chromometric method has made it possible to determine the kinetic parameters V_{max} and K_M for each enzyme. The highest binding affinity was shown by laccase. The antioxidant capacities of these two molecules have been characterized, finding a very similar primary antioxidant capacity between them. Docking studies revealed the optimal binding position, which was the same for the two molecules and was a catalytically active position.

(Curran et al., 2022)The search for seeking novel immobilized enzyme carriers is a hot topic in the field of enzyme engineering. As a kind of common office consumable, magnetic printing toner has been terribly wasted, leading to potential harm to the environment. We try to use printing toner as carrier for enzyme immobilization to realize waste reuse. In this paper, the laccase extracted from *Agaricus bisporus* was successfully immobilized on chitosan coated magnetic printing toner by glutaraldehyde linking. The use of printing toner is proved to be feasible. The results show that the optimal temperature of immobilized laccase is 40 °C, and the optimal pH is 3.0. Compared with free laccase, the optimal temperature and optimal pH have been obviously changed after immobilization. And

Chapter No. 2

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(da Silva et al.) Direct electrochemistry of oxidoreductase on electrode plays critical roles in the development of enzymatic biosensing and biofuel cells. Herein, a free-standing edge-rich graphene (ERG) film in-situ fabricated on a porous and conductive Si₃N₄ nanowires template with hydrophobic surface was directly used as a self-supporting electrode for site-directed capture of laccase from *Agaricus bisporus*. The ERG film possessed abundant edge-rich active sites, high conductivity, and especially hydrophobic surface, which realized the direct electron transfer of the immobilized laccase and its bioelectrocatalysis towards the O₂ reduction. With the comprehensive comparison to hydrophilic ERG, we found that the interfacial hydrophobicity played an important role for the orientated immobilization of laccase. Thereafter a faster electron transfer kinetic (1.32 vs. 0.74 s⁻¹) and a higher bioelectrocatalytic activity towards O₂ with over 10 times' enhancement in reductive current were achieved. This is probably because the hydrophobic region of laccase tends to specifically interact with the hydrophobic surface, allowing the site-directed capture of laccase on the hydrophobic ERG electrode.

(da Silva et al.) Co-immobilization of several enzymes on the same matrix might enhance the efficiency of bioremediation of water resources. In pursuit of this objective, laccase and tyrosinase are especially important due to their reliance on molecular oxygen during the oxidation of various compounds. Accordingly, in this research, the substrate spectra of a laccase (obtained from *Neurospora crassa*) and a tyrosinase (obtained from *Agaricus bisporus*) were studied through analysis of their reactions with different diazo derivatives of phenol, catechol, guaiacol, and aniline, which were made from an identical molecular structure. The results were explained in view of the influential parameters on the substrate selectivity of each enzyme. The outcome of this research indicates that co-immobilization of laccase with a tyrosinase possibly expands the spectrum of the target pollutants, however, it does not guarantee the efficacy of the system against aniline derivatives.

(Decarli et al., 2023) Frequently, laccases are triggered during fungal cocultivation for overexpression. The function of these activated laccases during coculture has not been

Chapter No. 2

clarified. Previously, we reported that *Gongronella* sp. w5 (w5) (Mucoromycota, Mucoromycetes) specifically triggered the laccase Lcc9 overexpression in *Coprinopsis cinerea* (Basidiomycota, Agaricomycetes). To systematically analyze the function of the overexpressed laccase during fungal interaction, *C. cinerea* mycelia before and after the initial Lcc9 overexpression were chosen for transcriptome analysis. Results showed that accompanied by specific utilization of fructose as carbohydrate substrate, oxidative stress derived from antagonistic compounds secreted by w5 appears to be a signal critical for laccase production in *C. cinerea*. A decrease in reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the *C. cinerea* wild-type strain followed the increase in laccase production, and then *lcc9* transcription and laccase activity stopped.

(DEVASIA & NAIR, 2023) Laccases have been broadly applied as a multitasking biocatalyst in various industries, but their applications tend to be limited by easy deactivation, lack of adequate stability, and susceptibility under complex conditions. Identifying stable laccase as a green-biocatalyst is crucial for developing cost-effective biorefining processes. In this direction, we attempted in-silico screening a stable metagenome-derived laccase (PersiLac1) from tannery wastewater in a complex environment. The laccase exhibited high thermostability, retaining 53.19% activity after 180 min at 70 °C, and it was stable in a wide range of pH (4.0–9.0). After 33 days of storage at 50°C, pH 6.0, the enzyme retained 71.65% of its activity. Various metal ions, inhibitors, and organic solvents showed that PersiLac1 has a stable structure. The stable PersiLac1 could successfully remove lignin and phenolic from quinoa husk and rice straw.

(Devi et al., 2023) Epigallocatechin-3-O-gallate (EGCG), one of the most abundant monomeric catechin compounds in green tea, was oxidized to EGCG dimers through radical oxidative reaction using laccase, a member of the tea polyphenol oxidase family. Electrospray ionization tandem LC-MS (ESI-LC/MS) was applied for the characterization of the dimers, including theacitrin, dehydrotheasinensin, and theasinensin, which were produced by the radical oxidative reaction. Chemical structures of the EGCG dimer were identified using LC/MS/MS and fragmentation patterns of EGCG dimer. The dimers were isomerized by heat treatment at 80°C after oxidation step to mimic heat treatment and drying in the last step of leaf fermentation. As a result of the heat treatment, theasinensin A (TSA) was formed as a major dimer product.

Chapter No. 2

(Dhagat & Jujjavarapu, 2023) Utilization of microbial laccases is considered as the cleaner and target specific biocatalytic mechanism for the recovery of cellulose and hemicelluloses from nonfood and wasted agricultural, lignocellulosic biomass (LCB). The extent of lignin removal by laccase depends on the biochemical composition of biomass and the redox potential (E^0) of the biocatalyst. Intensive research efforts are going on all over the world for the recognition of appropriate and easily available agricultural lignocellulosic feedstocks to exploit maximally for the production of value-added bioproducts and biofuels. In such circumstances, laccase can play a major role as a leading biocatalyst and potent substitute for chemical based deconstruction of the lignocellulosic materials. The limited commercialization of laccase at an industrial scale has been feasible due to its full working efficiency mostly expressed in the presence of cost intensive redox mediators only. Although, recently there are some reports that came on the mediator free biocatalysis of enzyme but still not considerably explored and neither understood in depth.

(Elhusseiny et al., 2023) Zwitterionic surfactants incorporated nanomaterials and biomolecules structures offers enhanced catalytic activities and stabilities in biosensing. Herein, we present the construction of biosensors using graphite, a class of imidazolium zwitterionic surfactants, 3-(1-alkyl-3-imidazolio)-propane-sulfonate (ImS3-n; n = 10, 12, 14, 16) and laccase (Lac) immobilized on clay halloysite nanotube (HNT) in a carbon paste electrode (CPE). The Lac-HNT-ImS3-14/CPE showed to be the most promising biosensor due to the low capacitance and fastest electronic charge transfer using the probe hexacyanoferrate. Therefore, the surfactant ImS3-14 was characterized by spectroscopic techniques such as ^1H , ^{13}C NMR and ESI-MS. The developed biosensor was used to create a novel electroanalytical method for the determination of dopamine by square-wave voltammetry (SWV). Under optimized conditions, the calibration plot showed a linear range for dopamine of 0.99–67.8 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ using SWV.

(Elsayed et al., 2023) In Mexico there are large areas of soils contaminated by hydrocarbons, causing economic and social damage to agricultural production, in this sense, the need to seek economic alternatives that allow contributing to the recovery of affected agricultural soils arises. The present work aimed to determine the biodegradation of diesel in an agricultural soil using residual substrates (RS) of *Agaricus bisporus*. Soil contaminated with 7 039 ppm of diesel was used with different doses of RS, incubated for 28 days at 37 °C. CO_2 production, diesel biodegradation, initial and final population of fungi, as well as specific enzymatic activity of initial and final laccases were determined. In all treatments,

Chapter No. 2

removal increased significantly ($p= 0.001$) at 37 °C, as well as CO₂ production rates. Treatment T4 had the highest percentage of diesel biodegradation (68.747%) and a final cumulative production of 6.144×10^{-4} mmol CO₂ m⁻³.

(Elsayed et al., 2023)Utilization of microbial laccases is considered as the cleaner and target specific biocatalytic mechanism for the recovery of cellulose and hemicelluloses from nonfood and wasted agricultural, lignocellulosic biomass (LCB). The extent of lignin removal by laccase depends on the biochemical composition of biomass and the redox potential (E^0) of the biocatalyst. Intensive research efforts are going on all over the world for the recognition of appropriate and easily available agricultural lignocellulosic feedstocks to exploit maximally for the production of value-added bioproducts and biofuels. In such circumstances, laccase can play a major role as a leading biocatalyst and potent substitute for chemical based deconstruction of the lignocellulosic materials. The limited commercialization of laccase at an industrial scale has been feasible due to its full working efficiency mostly expressed in the presence of cost intensive redox mediators only. Although, recently there are some reports that came on the mediator free biocatalysis of enzyme but still not considerably explored and neither understood in depth. The present review will address the various research gaps and shortcomings that acted as the big hurdles before the complete exploitation of laccases at an industrial scale.

(Flores et al., 2023)Laccase belongs to the superfamily of multicopper oxidases and has been widely investigated in recent decades. Due to its mild and efficient oxidation of substrates, laccase has been successfully applied in organic catalytic synthesis, the degradation of harmful substances, and other green catalytic fields. Nevertheless, there are few reports on the green catalysis with laccase. This review focuses on reporting and collating some of the latest interesting laccase-catalyzed bond formation and breakage research. This is discussed with a focus on the effects of the medium system on the laccase-catalyzed reaction, as well as the formation and the breakage of C–N, C–C, and C–O bonds catalyzed by laccase. It provides abundant references and novel insights for furthering the industrial applications of laccase.

(Fu et al., 2023)Global threat from emerging contaminants to human health has pushed researchers to develop pollutant removal technologies including those based on biocatalytic degradation. Laccase, a multicopper enzyme, is reported for its applicability in treating wastewater and industrial effluent by catalyzing reduction of O₂ to H₂O in the

Chapter No. 2

presence of substrates (phenolic or non-phenolic compounds). Scientific papers have discussed the ability of this enzyme to breakdown hazardous contaminants ranging from azo dyes, antibiotics, and up to hormones. Nonetheless, the cost production of this enzyme is high, hence the importance of the immobilization into solid supports. Polymers are considered suitable for the immobilization because they are easy for modification and have adjustable characteristics. This review discusses the immobilization of laccase into polymers via various techniques (adsorption, cross-linking, covalent binding, encapsulation, and entrapment) and its implications on the pollutant removal performance. In addition, bibliometric analysis is performed and summarized the advantages and disadvantages of each immobilization technique.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Spawn

Select healthy and clean wheat straw and boil in water (15-20 min.). Remove excess water on sieve. And dry in shade Incubate for 20-25 days (shake after 10 days) and the Spawn is ready

Spawning and Filling of bags and trays

For spawning, the mixed spawning method was used. Mixing of wheat grain-based spawn was done @ 2 kg per 100 kg compost of *Agaricus bisporus* under clean conditions (i.e., with clean hands and a pre-sterilized area). Good quality compost with a temperature of 25 °C was used. Then fill spawned compost into polythene bags (size 16" x 22") to a depth of 10-12". Little compressing and leveling of spawned compost was done.

Casing

A mixture was prepared and sterilized. It was added up to 3 cm on top of the spawn run compost. Sterilization was done by making a heap of casing material on a cemented platform and wetting up to 50-60% water holding capacity. The wet casing was drenched by mixing with the shovel. It was then covered with a polythene sheet and the outer periphery was sealed. The material was kept for 24-48 hrs. The cover was removed after 48 hrs.' and the material was exposed to open air and sunlight by spreading over with clean tools and permitting to escape into air for 2-3 days before it was used as casing.

Cropping

Under favorable environmental conditions viz. temperature initially 23 ± 2 °C for about a week and then 16 ± 2 °C), moisture (2-3 light sprays per day for moistening the casing layer), humidity (above 85%), proper ventilation and CO₂ concentration (0.08-0.15 %) the fruit body initials which appeared in the form of pinheads started growing and gradually developed into button stage. The first crop appeared about three weeks after casing. Mushrooms were harvested by gentle twisting and soil end parts were cut off. After harvesting was complete, the gaps in the beds were filled with fresh sterilized casing material and then watered. Yield data for average weight and total yield of fruiting bodies per bag was recorded

Crude protein extraction

SDS-PAGE Electrophoresis

Primary Sequence Analysis of AbL

AbL sequence was retrieved from the NCBI database <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov> with NCBI Accession No. ACC18877. Translated protein sequence from this gene was also retrieved from this gene sequence by NCBI Accession No.: ACC18877 This enzyme sequence can also be retrieved from the UniProtKB database (<https://www.uniprot.org>) by (UniProtKB ID: Q12541).

Multiple Sequence Alignment and Sequence Homology Analysis

After retrieval of the FASTA sequence of AbL, BLAST-P was run on the NCBI website with PDB selected as the database. A homology modeling template search was done on the SWISS-MODEL to get the most suitable template for AbL. Possible templates for the AbL were selected depending on different values, and multiple sequence alignment (MSA) was done on Clustal Omega, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo/>, which is a multiple sequence alignment program that produces biologically meaningful multiple sequence alignments of divergent sequences. A percentage Identity matrix homology table among those selected templates was built by this alignment.

Multiple sequence alignment was done on the ESPript 3 server for proper understating of the homology sequence. The alignment file was downloaded from the Clustal Omega server, and the predicted model of AbL was uploaded to the ESPript 3 server to get the MSA (<https://espript.ibcp.fr/ESPript/ESPript/index.php>). It is a tool of choice for biologists, and structural biologists, enabling production with a few mouse clicks, a collection of comprehensive, high-quality figures, and interactive 3D representations of their proteins of interest. With its simplified interface and capacity to rapidly generate the significant properties of any protein structure, it is also an efficient instructional tool that may be used during courses or practical work sessions in structural biology among these templates (Robert & Gouet, 2014).

Phylogenetic Tree

Chapter No. 3

A phylogenetic tree among all the possible selected templates was constructed. An accurate phylogenetic tree is essential for inferring the genesis of novel genes, identifying molecular adaptation, comprehending morphological feature evolution, and recreating demographic changes in recently separated species. The Neighbor-Joining approach was used to infer the evolutionary history (Saitou & Nei, 1987). The Poisson correction technique was used to calculate the evolutionary distances in the units of the number of amino acid substitutions per site (Zuckerandl & Pauling, 1965). This study comprised five amino acid sequences. All ambiguous sites were deleted for each sequence pair (pairwise deletion option).

Three Dimensional Structure Prediction of AbL

FASTA sequence of AbL was uploaded on the SWISS-MODEL (<https://swissmodel.expasy.org/>) online server (Waterhouse et al., 2018). It is a web-based integrated service focused on protein structure homology modeling. The SWISS-MODEL database includes automatically produced homology models for appropriate model organisms and quantitative structural information for all UniProtKB sequences. It aids the user in generating protein homology models at various degrees of complexity. Structure building through this server includes the five steps: (i) Input data (ii) Template search (iii) Template selection (iv) Model building (v) Model quality estimation.

The predicted structure was downloaded in PDB format, and all its essential sites were highlighted and labeled along with its domains in PyMOL software (The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.5.2 Schrödinger, and LLC). The predicted model of AbL was uploaded on the PDBsum. This web server gives a summary and visual assessment of empirically verified macromolecular structure models in the Protein Data Bank (PDB). In addition, the PDBsum server enables you to submit your PDB-format data and produce and file a whole collection of PDBsum structural analyses and schematics diagrams depicting the interactions (Laskowski, 2001). A 2D structure was generated and labeled with helices, beta sheets, loops, all crucial residues, and domains.

Structure Refinement and Validation

The predicted model of AbL was refined on the Galaxy refine webserver (<https://galaxy.seoklab.org/>). A significant characteristic of the server from existing protein

Chapter No. 3

structure servers is that unreliable sections for which template information is not accessible or inconsistent are recognized and refined using an *initio* process (Ko *et al.*, 2012). This refined model can be used for the next step of docking after validation.

The generated model from SWISS-MODEL was validated at the Molecular Biology Institute and the DOE-MBI Institute online servers at the University of California, Los Angeles (<https://saves.mbi.ucla.edu/>) online server. The structure was validated in many ways, like ERRAT, Ramachandran plot, VERIFY 3D, etc.

ERRAT is based on the concept that various atom types will be distributed non-randomly in proteins owing to complicated geometric and energetic considerations. Structural flaws would result in visible abnormalities in the pattern of interactions. The following constraints apply to the evaluation of non-bonded interactions: the gap in space between two atoms is smaller than some predetermined limit, often 3.5 Å, and atoms within the same residue or those covalently bound to one another are not regarded. This distribution is used to assess the likelihood that a particular collection of interactions from a protein model is accurate. Because the ERRAT assessment is based on a standard distribution calibrated on a credible database, estimating the chance that each area of a candidate protein model is wrong is simple. This approach identifies erroneously generated areas in protein models in an impartial and statistically sound manner (Colovos & Yeates, 1993).

The PROCHECK suite of programs checks the stereochemistry of a protein structure in detail. Its outputs include a variety of PostScript graphics and a complete residue-by-residue listing. These provide an evaluation of the model's overall quality compared to well-refined structures of the same resolution, as well as highlighting locations that may need more examination (Laskowski *et al.*, 1993).

The Ramachandran plot is critical in identifying the stereochemical quality of the protein model. The conformation angles, also known as the Ramachandran angles, dictate the backbone of a protein molecule's polypeptide chain. In the Ramachandran Plot, these angles are plotted against one other. The Ramachandran plot is a powerful tool for analyzing the conformation angles of any three-dimensional structure determined using X-ray crystallography or NMR. Users may upload the three-dimensional atomic coordinates of a protein molecule of interest from the client machine (Gopalakrishnan *et al.*, 2007).

Chapter No. 3

The compatibility of a 3D protein model to its amino acid sequence, as determined by a 3D profile, is an effective test of the model's accuracy. A protein structure's 3D profile is a table generated from the structure's atomic coordinates that may be used to score the compatibility of the three-dimensional structure model with any amino acid sequence. High-scoring three-dimensional profiles generated from proper protein structures match their sequences. In contrast, 3D profiles computed from incorrect protein models perform poorly. Using a 3D profile, the approach assesses the compatibility of a protein model with its sequence. Each residue location in the 3D model is defined by its environment and is represented in the profile by a row of 20 integers. These are the statistical preferences (referred to as 3D-1D scores) of each of the 20 amino acids in this environment (Eisenberg *et al.*, 1997).

Structural Alignment of AbL and its template

After selecting the template, the alignment between the template and target sequence was constructed in the PyMOL program and their RMSD values were interpreted. The structural differences between two ideally aligned models are commonly assessed as the Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) between the aligned alpha-carbon locations (excluding deviations from the non-aligned positions). To offer a frame of reference for RMSD measurements, up to 0.5 Å RMSD of alpha carbons occurs in separate determinations of the same protein. An optimum RMSD value is always less than 1 Å.

Phytochemical compounds Selection

The phytochemical compounds database, having many molecules was selected for virtual screening against AbL to find potential inhibitors to stop its functioning. These compounds database was chosen from the PubChem Classification Browser (well-known and reliable chemical compound [.https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/classification/#hid=5](https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/classification/#hid=5)).

Molecular Docking of AbL with Glycerol

Molecular docking of AbL was done with the natural substrate Glycerol (GLU) to get the residues interacting with AbL active site. The binding pocket for this docking, and the docking score was also observed. Virtual screening of small ligand molecules helps to find potential inhibitors against proteins or enzymes by site-directed target-based docking. The

Chapter No. 3

MOE (Molecular Orbiting Environment) module has been used in a lot of research to carry out molecular docking of different ligands against several biological targets. Molecular docking of the selected phytochemicals was done in the MOE (v2015) <https://www.chemcomp.com/>.

Preparation of Protein Structure

The protein structure was prepared in module by uploading the predicted protein structure in PDB format. Using Protonate 3D, the hydrogen bond networks were re-optimized. In the context of an all-atom model of a macromolecular structure, the Protonate 3D program assigns protonation states from a discrete collection of states by minimizing the titration free energy of all groups (including ligands and solvents).

Preparing Ligand Database

All ligands downloaded from were uploaded in SDF file format; all of them were energy minimized by default parameters, and the ligands database was saved. All ligands are typically utilized in their pre-reacted state. If necessary, manual structure alterations are made otherwise, they are used directly from their source database.

Analysis of AbL

Docking of the natural substrate, GLU, was done with AbL, and its interacting residues forming hydrogen bonds were used as active sites of AbL. Site finder feature is available which tells us about the binding pockets present in the protein or enzyme. The site finder indicated binding pockets; a search was done for which pocket had residues interacting with the natural substrate. So, Site 1 was found suitable, and dummy atoms were created at the selected binding pocket.

Docking Analysis

Docking results obtained were analyzed in PyMOL, which was used for the generation of protein and ligand cartoon models, and LigPlot software was used for the development of LigPlot images and analysis of molecular interactions of different complexes.

RESULTS

Chapter No. 4

For the majority of us, *Agaricus bisporus* is the type of industrial fungus most commonly found on pizza and available in grocery shops. It comes in a variety of shapes, including button, brown, and big Porto variations, all of which belong to the same species. Its popularity is more a result of its adaptability for industrial use than of the flavor as a whole. However, all of the *Agaricus* mushrooms sold in stores are cultivated on a controlled media and in a controlled environment, sometimes in caves or underground constructions, not so much for the darkness but because of the constant temperatures and high humidities. *Agaricus* does grow wild, typically in fields or lawns.

A thorough analysis outlining the nutritional, pharmacological, and cosmetic benefits of *A. bisporus* as well as identifying the research gaps is offered to emphasize various elements of the plant. By doing this, it would be feasible to increase the number and quality of bioactive chemicals in *A. bisporus*, which might eventually aid in the identification of novel therapeutics and the underlying mechanisms. We highlight the most recent discoveries about the dietary, medicinal, and aesthetic benefits of *A. bisporus* in this article. Research gaps and potential future directions are also highlighted.

In terms of understanding the gastronomic and therapeutic benefits of mushrooms, *A. bisporus* has broadened the world's perspective. Tyrosinase and ergothioneine have been isolated from this fungus in recent years, making it more valuable to consider for dietary and therapeutic applications. *Agaricus* and almost all other fungi that produce stalked structures with a cap, or that would be classified as mushrooms, are club fungi, also known as basidiomycete fungi (Phylum Basidiomycota). The majority of mushrooms have 'gills' where spores are formed on the underside of the cap, and *Agaricus* exhibits this characteristic.

Like most creatures, *Agaricus* depends heavily on its interactions with other organisms and its physical surroundings to survive. The websites below that discuss how mushrooms are raised commercially reflect this. *Agaricus*, as previously mentioned, is referred to as a "secondary decomposer" since it consumes material that has already been consumed by "primary decomposers." This is comparable to how cows and the microbes in their stomachs interact. Even while the order Agaricales, which bears *Agaricus'* name, still exists, it does not include all gilled mushrooms and does include a few fungi that do not. A growing number of

Chapter No. 4

byproducts from their industrial production are a direct result of *Agaricus bisporus*, which constitutes a significant food sector in Europe.

Preparation of compost

First of all we have to prepare the compost. Compost is basically prepared with the help of animal manure and wheat straw. They are mixed well with the 1:1 ratio and the after few times later the spawn is inserted in it. This preparation takes few weeks in which proper

water, air
is
for proper
compost.
with
straw

and care
important
and well
It starts
wheat

collection. It is taken out from the collection in a separate plate and placed in a vessel having boiling water. This is done so because to sterilize wheat straw.

Chapter No. 4

Fig. 1. A is showing the sample of wheat straw that is taken from the collection. This will be boiled for the sterilization purpose in a separate vessel.

B is showing the total collection of wheat straw present in a carton box. According to our needs, we take the sample out of the collection.

Sterilization process

First of all, water is taken in a vessel and boiled at high flame. The purpose is to get the boiling point of water. When it is done, wheat straw is taken in a separate vessel and added to that boiled water and mixed continuously with the help of a stirrer so that there should be proper mixing and sterilization process. This is clearly shown in the diagram below.

Fig. 2. C is showing that the sample of wheat straw is taken and is added to the boiling water. The purpose of all this is to sterilize it.

D is showing that loading of wheat straw is done in the vessel.

Fig. 3. A is showing that the wheat straw is added and well mixing is being done with the help of stirrer so that there should be proper mixing up. The flame is high which means the constant heating and mixing is necessary for proper results.

B is showing that mixing and stirring is done. It is time to take these wheat straw out of that boiling water with the help of strainer and it should be done with proper care.

Fig. 4. A is showing that the sample of wheat straw is taken out of boiling water and the place where it has to be placed is cleaned properly and is taken on the newspaper to avoid from germs.

Chapter No. 4

B is showing the manure sample is taken in a separate vessel. This manure is also vital in the preparation of compost.

Well mixing of wheat straw and manure

Fig. 5. A is showing that compost is being prepared with the help of wheat straw. Equal amount of manure and wheat straw is taken in a separate vessel with ratio of 1:1

B is showing that after the equal samples are taken there is well mixing of the compost with the help of protected and safe hands

Vessels to keep that compost

There are different kinds of vessel that are used to keep that compost having spawn and manure. Here we are going to take a large sized bucket having holes so that there should be proper aeration and trays of different types are taken. Different cleaned and sterilized newspapers are also taken with can help to cover that compost to avoid any kind of dirt or germs etc.

Fig. 6. A is showing a vessel commonly a bucket having the different kinds of holes on the front side for the purpose of proper aeration

B is showing the tray where we have to insert the compost and the spawn for proper growth. This should be neat and clean.

Organized Compost

Fig. 7. A is showing that the compost is ready and taken in a bucket having holes for proper stay and we have to keep that until the growth of spawn starts

B is showing that the compost is taken in a tray that is covered the newspaper

Growth of mushroom

Fig. 8. A is showing that the growth of the mushroom has been started and a small part of this can be shown in the diagram

Chapter No. 4

B is showing that the white coloured portions have spawn of mushroom that are ready to grow

White button mushroom

White button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) is grown. *Agaricus* does grow wild, typically in fields or lawns but all of the *Agaricus* mushrooms sold in stores are grown on a controlled medium and in a controlled environment, often in caves or underground structures, not so much for the darkness but because of constant temperatures and high humidity. *Agaricus*, and nearly all of the fungi that would be described as mushrooms, i.e. that produce stalked structures with a cap, are club fungi = basidiomycete fungi (Phylum Basidiomycota).

Fig. 9. **A** is showing that finally the white button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) is grown. The complete shape is clear having cap, stalk and roots etc.

B is showing that an obvious button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) is present and well grown in a vessel along with other spawn samples.

Gel electrophoresis

Chapter No. 4

The process of gel electrophoresis is done for the purpose of getting the bands. This process was done again and again and finally a band of 50KDa was obtained

Fig. 10. The process of gel electrophoresis is done for the purpose of getting the bands. This process was done again and again and finally a band of 50KDa was obtained on 05-03-2023 that can be seen with the help of diagram shown above.

Agaricus bisporus secretes abundant laccase activity into the medium during mycelial growth. SDS-PAGE analysis of extracellular laccase protein, purified from compost extract, showed a predominant band of 50 KDa molecular mass, together with lesser amounts of smaller polypeptides. The main polypeptide was purified electrophoretically. Amino acid sequence analysis of the N-terminal region of the main polypeptide was used to specify the sequence of a 15-residue chemically synthesized peptide (N-terminal peptide). Rabbit antibodies were raised against pure laccase, electrophoretically purified main polypeptide and the synthetic N-terminal peptide. Electrophoretically purified main polypeptide antibody was further purified by affinity chromatography on laccase-CNBr-Sepharose. Western blot analysis showed that the antigenic behaviour of laccase in compost extract, culture filtrate from malt-extract culture, and the purified enzyme from both sources, differed.

FASTA Sequences of AbL

Chapter No. 4

FASTA sequence of *Agaricus bisporus* laccase was retrieved from NCBI database (Accession No ACC18877).

```
CTACGTCTTGACAGTATGTCTCTGAAGCACATTGTTAATCATGAGCGAACCTAAG
GCCGATTTAGCTACGGTGAGTCGTGACCAACGTCCAGTGGCAAAGCGCTGGTTTT
AGTATTAATCACAACTGAACCACAGTACAACGCCTGCAAGACACGCGCGTGA
TGTTCAATACAAACGTTGAACATCTATGCGCCTGTAACGGGGAGAGAAACCTCG
TGAAACTGCCCTGGATGATAAATTCATCAGCTTCGAATGTCAGTGACATTGAAT
GTTATAAATACCCAGCAGAGAGTGGCTCGTCCTCAATGTGAGCGCGTAAACTTTA
GAAAATTTCCGTGGATTGTGGTCTCAGGCATATCGCTGGTGGTTTTCTCCTTGTGTA
TAAAAATATGTATCTTCAGGCTATAAAGACGGGGGCAGAGGACCGTGGATTGAC
TCTCCAGCGGTAGGATCAACAATGAGGCTGTCCAACGCTTTAGTATTGGTCGCCG
CATGCATTTGAGTGTAGTTGCGAAAACCAGAACCTTCGACTTCGACCTAGTCAA
TACCAGGCTCGCGCCTGATGGGTTTGAAAGGGAGTGAGTATATTTCTATACAGAT
TCATCGTTAGAGTTTACTGACCTTGATTTAAACTAGCACCGTGGTCATCAATGGA
GAATTCCCTGGAACACTGATCCAAGTCAACAAGGGCGACAGTGTCCGCATCCCT
CTCCATAACAACTGACTAGCCCGACCATGAGGCGAAGTGTATCCATTGTGAGTT
ACTTTTTGAGCCCAGATTGACTTGACTATATAACACAAATTAGCATTGGCATGGA
TTTTTCCAAGCGAGA ACTTCTGGTCAGGACGGGCCTTCCTTCGTGAATCAGTGCC
CTCAGCCACCCAACACAACCTTCACCTATGAATTCAGCGTGGCGGAGCAGTCTGG
AACGTTTCGTCCTGATCCCTTAAATACATCTTCAGCGTAAATTGACATTTCTTCAAG
TTATTGGTACCATTCACTTGTCCACCCAATACTGTGATGGTCTTCGCGGTGCAT
TCATCGTTTACGGTAATTCCTTCCTCTTGCATGCGAAGATATTTTTGCGACTTTCG
TTTAGACCCACGTGATCCACTCAGACATCTCTATGATGTTGATGACAAGTACCGT
CATCACTCTAGCTGAATGGTATCACATCCTCGCACCCGATGCCACTACGAGTTTT
TCAGCTCTGGCATTATACCGTAAGCTTCTTAAAGGAATATTTATTCATTTTCATAA
CCCAATTCCTGCAGCGTGCAAGATTCTGGCTTGATCAACGGTAAGGTAGATTCAA
TGGAGGACCCCTCAGTAAGTAGATCAAAACAGAAAAGGTGATGATGAAAATTTG
ACTTTACTTGCTTAGCACCATTCGCCGTCGTCAATGTTTCGCCGAGGAAACGTTAC
AGGCTCCGTGTCATAGCTATTTCTTGCAGGCCGTTCTTCACCTTCTCCGTCGATAA
CCATAGCTTGGTCTTCATGGAAGCCGATGGTGTGTAACATGACCCTGTCGAAGTC
CAAAACGTCGACATCTACGCGGCCAGCGTGTCTCGGTTATTCTGCATGCCAATC
AACCCATCGATAACTACTGGATCAGAGCTCCTATGACTGGCGGCAACCCAGACA
GGAACCCCAATCGTAAGCGTCATTTTGCCACCTGCTAGCAGCTGTAATGAAACGT
GTTTCAAAGTAAACATCAGCCTCACTCTCGCCATCCTGCGCTACCATGGTGCAC
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Chapter No. 4

GTCACGTCGAACCGACTACGGTCAACGTTCCCGGACACAACTCCTTGATCAAG
AAATGCATGTAAGAATAACTTGCGTAAAGGCATTCCGAAATACTTACAACGCGC
ACCAATCTAGCCGATCCGCCAGGAAGGACCAGGCAAAGTGTGTATATATTTACA
TGAACATAATCATCAACTCAACGTTCTCTAGCTCGGTGACGGTCCCCCGATAAG
CACATCACCTCAACATTGCTCAAGTAAGCGTCTCATTATTCAAATCAAACCTCGA
CTTCTGACATGAGCACAGCCCAACGCTCCCTTCTTCGATATCAACGGAATCTCTT
ACATCTCCCCGACTGTCCCTGTTCTTCTCCAAATCCTCAGCGGAGCCAAGAGGCC
CGAAGATGTTCTTCCATCCGAACAAATCTTCTTTGTCCCCAAGAATTCATTGATTG
AAGTCAACATTCCAGGAGAAGGAGCTCATCCATTCCATTGTATGGTAACCTCATT
TTCTCCTCAATTCCTCTACTTACGTCCCTGTTTCAGTGCACGGTCATAACTTTGAT
GTCGTTCTGGCTTCTAACGACGACACTTTCAACTTCAAGAAGTGAGTTAATTGAA
AAAGGAAGTTACCTGCTGAACACTAATCTCAAATGAAAGCCCGCCTCGTCGTGA
CGTATACCCCATCAACGGTGGCAACACCACTTTCCGCTTCTGTAAGATTCCACGT
TTCTTTCTGAAGAATAACTCTTTCTGAACGACCCCTCAGTCACCGATAAACCAGG
CGCATGGTTCTTGCATTGGTGAGGAACATTTCTATCCATTTCTCTCGAGGCGAAT
ACTGATTGAATCTTGTGACATAGCCATATCGATTGGCATCTTGAAGCTGGTCTCG
CTATTGTGTTTGCTGAGGCTCCGGAGGATAACGTTTCAGGTCCCCAGTCTCAGAT
CACTCCTCAAGATTGGTTGGATCTCTGTCCAGAATACAACGCAATCGAGCCTGAA
TTCCAGTAGTTTATTCAAATATTTATATTCCTCTCACAAGGAAATCTATCTCTGTG
TACAAGTAGGAATTTTAAACAATGTTTACCCTAAAACAAAATGATCGTAAGTATT
AAGTGGCGGCATTAACGAGGCAGGTAGTAATGATAACAAACCCAGGCACTTGAT
GCGCTTTGAATTGAAGTCTTAAGGGCCCATGTGTAACAAGAATGCATTCACTGAC
ACGACCATGAGACTCCGAACGGTCTATATGGCACTGTCACAAGGTGATGAGTGA
AGATAGAACAAGTTTACCCAGATCTGCTGAAGTTGCTGATCCTGGCAGACTGTCCG
ATTCTCACGGAGCCTTAAATTCTTCCCATGCTCATTGGCATCAGTTCCCACTGTCA
CTCGCACGATTACACATGCGAGATGACATTGTTGAGCGTATGAAAGTACTTCCA
GGAAGTAATATAAATCATATTAGCGAGATAATATTGACAATGTTTGGGAAATTTT
CTCATAGTGAGTTTACATCCGGCTCTAACTGAAGATAGGCAGGTACTCCAATGA
GATGCCTCCAAATTACCTTCAATCATCCAGTCCAAATTGCACTGCAAAGTATTTT
GCGCTTCCACGGCACGTCCCTCAACAATATACTAAATAAATGATTCTTAATGAT
TCGGCGGTATGGCCGCCTTATTGAAGGTCGGCGGCGCATTGGAATCTTCAATTTT
GGCAATCTATATGGTCCACGCCTCTCCGTGCTTACTGCTTAGTGAAGCGGCGAAG

Chapter No. 4

The FASTA sequence of AbL enzyme was retrieved from the translated protein sequence from that gene (NCBI Accession No. ACC 18877). This sequence can also be retrieved from UniProt ID: Q12541 in the UniProtKB database. Both sequences were the same with Taxonomic identifier in NCBI.

```
MRFSNAFVLVAACISSVLADTKTFNFDLVNTRLAPDGFERDTVVINGEFPGTLVQVN
KGDSVRIPVNNKLTSSSTMRRSVSIHWHGFFQARTSGQDGPAFVNQCPQPPNTTFTYE
FSVADESGTFWYHSHLSTQYCDGLRGAFVVYDPEDPLGHLVDVDETTVITLAEWY
HVLAPDINNEFFSSGIIPVQDSGLINGKGRFNNGPETPFAVVNVEQGKRYRFRVIAISC
RPFFTFSVDNHNLTfMEADSVEHDPVEIQNVDIYAAQRVSVILNANQPVDNYWMRA
PMTGGNPDRNPNLNISLTLAILRYKGAPEVEPTTVNVPGHKLLDQEMHPIAQEGPGK
LGDGPPDKHITLNIQPNAPFFDINGISYISPTVPVLLQILSGAKRPEDVLPSEQIFFVPK
NSLIEVNIPGEGAHPFHLHGHNFDVVLASNDDTFNFVNPPRRDVYPINGGNTTFRFFT
DNPgAWFLHCHIDWHLEAGLAIVFAEAPEDNVSGPQSQITPQDWL DLCPEYNAIEPE
```

Homology Table

Four possible templates PDB ID: 3FPX, PDB ID: 3PXL, PDB ID: 5MHU and PDB ID: 5A7E) were selected by homology sequence search. All these chosen templates had query coverage greater than 98% and percentage identity greater than 98%.

Sequence homology percentage identity matrix was observed, and a homology table (Table 1) was built (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/services/rest/clustalo/result/clustalo-I20220816-142744-0204-91031055-p1m/pim>) after the multiple sequence alignment in Clustal Omega server.

Table 1. Sequence homology table between the AbL enzyme with possible templates shows that the enzyme is much similar to template.

Sr. No.	Enzymes	Homologies (%)
1	ACC1	100.00
2	5MHU	49.28
3	5A7E	48.66
4	3PXL	48.87
5	3FPX	48.87

Multiple Sequence Alignment

For the proper understanding of the comparative relationship among all these structures (mentioned in Table 1), Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA) was done on the Clustal Omega online server, and then from the ESPrict 3 server, the similarity MSA (Fig. 1)

Chapter No. 4

was obtained. This is shown in the below-given diagram.

Fig. 1. MSA of AbL and templates was drawn by ESPript 3 server. Identical and similar residues are shown in red and yellow boxes, respectively. Secondary structures of AbL are displayed at the top of aligned sequences. Helices are represented in squiggles, β - strands in arrows, and turns are indicated in TT letters.

Phylogenetic Tree

A phylogenetic tree was constructed (Fig. 2) to see the evolutionary taxa of these AbL and its possible templates and to select the most suitable template. The tree showed that 3PXL is the nearest and best template for structure prediction among them. Although data are becoming more numerous and strong analytic tools are accessible, there are several barriers

to trustworthy tree construction.

Fig. 2. Phylogenetic tree of AbL and templates represents that PDB ID: 3PXL is the closest relative of AbL as compared to other templates. It also indicates that it can be the best template for 3D structure prediction of AbL

Secondary Structure of AbL

AbL has a molecular weight of 50.064 KDa, and it contains a total of 520 amino acids. Secondary structural conformations of the predicted model of AbL were generated.

Chapter No. 4

Sec. struc: Helices labelled H1, H2, ... and strands by their sheets A, B, ...
HelixStrand
Motifs: β beta turn γ gamma turn beta hairpin
Disulphides: disulphide bond
Residue contacts: to metal

Fig. 4. Secondary structure of AbL represents the helices in purple, which are H1-H18; beta sheets are shown in yellow arrows, and loops are indicated in brown lines. Domains of AbL are shown in rod-shaped lines above the primary sequences, C-terminal in domain 1 (residues 1 to 18 and 232 to 418) in blue color and N-terminal in domain 2 (residues 22 to 228). Residues in the pink background show the double-stranded linker peptides

ERRAT for AbL

The ERRAT quality factor was found to be 86.558%. (Fig. 5). ERRAT shows the proportion of interactions of non-bonded atoms in the structure. The quality score >90% shows the most reliable structures and is produced mainly by better quality structures. About >90% quality factor (produced by lower resolutions 2.5-3.0 Å) is acceptable to consider the structure

Fig5. ERRAT shows an overall quality factor of 86.5%. On the error value axis, two lines

Chapter No. 4

(yellow and red) are drawn, indicating the residues disturbing the structure's overall quality. These show the confidence with which it is possible to reject regions that will exceed that error value. The more the quality factor of the structure, the more reliable the structure is.

Ramachandran Plot for AbL

Ramachandran plot was obtained from the PROCHECK to evaluate backbone conformations and stereochemical quality of the modeled structure by Φ - ψ plot. In a Ramachandran plot, the white regions represent conformations where atoms in the polypeptide approach are closer than the total of their van der Waals radius. These areas are sterically forbidden for all amino acids except glycine, which is unusual because it lacks a side chains The red sections correspond to conformations where there are no steric conflicts, i.e., these are the authorized regions, notably the alpha-helical and beta-sheet conformations. The yellow areas illustrate the permissible regions if slightly shorter van der Waals radii are employed in the computation, i.e., the atoms are allowed to move a bit closer together. This brings out an extra area that corresponds to the left-handed alpha-helix.

Ramachandran plot for AbL (Fig. 6) revealed that 85.9% with 359 residues are present in the most favored regions, 12.4% with 52 residues in the additional allowed regions, and 1.2% residues are present in the generously allowed and the disallowed areas. Total residues are 503, no. of non-glycine and non-proline residues are 418, no. of end residues (excl. Glycine and Proline) are 2, no. of glycine residues are 36 and no. of proline residues are 44. A good quality structure has more than 90% residues in the most favored regions.

Fig. 6. Ramachandran plot for AbL. Regions [A, B, L] show the most favored regions, [a, b, l, p] indicate the additional allowed regions, [~a, ~b, ~l, ~p] show the generously allowed regions, while the remaining white region shows the disallowed regions.

VERIFY 3D

VERIFY 3D results showed that 83.20% of the structure residues have averaged 3D-1D score ≥ 0.1 . At least 80% of the amino acids have scored ≥ 0.1 in the 3D/1D profile.

Fig. 7. VERIFY 3D for AbL indicated that 83.20% of all residues had averaged 3D-1D scores greater than 0.1. It represents that the structure is highly reliable

Structure Prediction**Predicted model of AbL**

From the SWISS-MODEL templates generated for AbL enzyme, from *Agaricus bisporus* (PDB ID: 3PXL) was selected as a template because of its high coverage, high sequence identity (46.63%), high resolution (X-ray, 1.2Å) from PDB, and high Global Model Quality Estimate (GMQE) = 0.81 and Quaternary Structure Quality Estimate (QSQE) = 0.54 values as compared to other templates and 3D model of AbL was generated.

Fig. 3. 3D predicted model of AbL shows that it is composed of 2 domains shown in different colors. The model is represented in a cartoon model with domain 1 in blue color and domain 2 in green color. A double-stranded linker peptide connects the two domains and is illustrated in pink, while the PEP binding region is indicated in orange.

Structural Alignments of AbL

Structural alignment of predicted AbL (Fig. 8) with its template (PDB ID:3PXL) was done on the PyMOL Visualization Software version 2.5.2, which showed that alpha/beta arrangement, three-dimensional structure, functional domain, and conserved residues are similar by the superimposition of AbL and RMSD value of 1.38 Å was obtained.

Fig. 8. Structural alignment of AbL with its template model showed the RMSD value of 1.38 Å. The template model is shown in blue color and AbL in green color. These validation results demonstrated that modeled 3D structure is exceptional and exhibits excellent structural integrity and stability. This evaluation and analysis conclude that the *Agaricus bisporus* AbL model generated in the current work is trustworthy for defining future protein-substrate, protein-ligand interactions and analyzing the link between the structure and function.

Molecular Docking of AbL and Glycerol

Obtain the *Agaricus bisporus* laccase 3D structure from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) or, in the absence of one, use homology modelling to predict the structure. Remove any ions, water molecules, or other tiny molecules that aren't a part of the enzyme to prepare the protein structure. Assign atom kinds and include any extra atoms required for a full structure. Build the 3D structure of glycerol using molecular modelling tools or obtain it from chemical

Chapter No. 4

databases. Glycerol should be converted to the proper 3D structure format, such as PDB, SDF,

Molecular docking between AbL and Glycerol can help predict how Glycerol interacts with the enzyme's active site and estimate the strength of their binding affinity

Molecular docking of AbL with the Glycerol was performed by using the binding pocket of the template (PDB ID:2QT6). It showed some residues of the AbL which interacted by forming H-bonds with ligand atoms (Fig. 9). These interacting residues were taken as the active binding site residues.

Fig. 9 represents that the GLU formed H-bonds with Val 79, Gln 105, and Tyr 113 with specific binding free energy (-6.7 kcal/mol) and RMSD value of 1.38 Å (Table 2). Molecular interactions between protein and GLU were analyzed via PyMOL-generated ball and stick protein model and LigPlot was generated with the help of PDBsum generate and downloaded

Table 2. Docking result analysis of natural substrate Glycerol and AbL indicating docking score, RMSD value, interacting residues with bond lengths, and 2D structure

PubChem ID	Chemical 2D structure of Ligand	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	RMSD Å	Residues forming H-bonds	Distance Å
GLU 753		-6.7	1.38	VAL79 GLN105 TYR113	2.51 2.83 2.73

Chapter No. 4

Fig. 9. Docking analysis of AbL GLU complex. (A) is showing the interactions in PyMOL, and (B) indicates the LigPlot analysis. It is evident that the ligand molecule makes 3 H-bonds (indicated by dashed lines) with the AbL active site residues (Val79, Gln105, and Tyr113).

DISCUSSION

Chapter No. 5

White button mushrooms are small to medium in size with caps averaging 2-7 centimeters in diameter and are attached to short, truncated stems. The smooth white caps are rounded, firm, and spongy. When bruised, the white flesh will turn light pink and will then transform into brown. Underneath the unopened caps, there are many small, light brown gills that are hidden with a white veil and these gills produce dark brown spores. The short white stem is also edible, dense, thick, and smooth. When raw, White button mushrooms are mild with a crisp texture, and when cooked, they develop an earthy flavor with a tender, chewy texture.

The FASTA sequence of *Agaricus bisporus* was retrieved from NCBI (Accession No ACC18877) along with the translated protein sequence. The BLAST program was run, Multiple sequence alignment was done, a Phylogenetic tree was constructed, and SWISS-MODEL values were observed. All these parameters suggested that was the closest template. This template has a sequence homology percentage of 48.87%. Three-dimensional structure was predicted by an online 3D structure predicting server, SWISS-MODEL. The predicted structure was validated by ERRAT, Ramachandran plot, and VERIFY 3D values. These findings showed that the overall ERRAT quality factor output in the minimized AbL model was 86.558%. ERRAT showed the percentage of non-bonded interactions between different atoms for which the estimated error score fell below the 90% rejection threshold.

Some residues are present in the rejection area because they are not correctly crystallized in the template model during X-Ray Crystallography, and they are also causing disturbance here. Ramachandran plot was obtained from the PROCHECK for the evaluation of backbone conformations, and stereochemical quality of the modeled structure by Φ - ψ plot, Ramachandran plot for AbL (Fig. 6) revealed that 85.9% with 359 residues are present in the most favored regions, 12.4% with 52 residues in the additional allowed regions, and 1.2% residues are present in the generously allowed and the disallowed areas. Total residues are 503, no. of non-glycine and non-proline residues are 418, no. of end residues (excl. Glycine and Proline) are 2, no. of glycine residues are 36 and no. of proline residues are 44. A good quality structure has more than 90% residues in the most favored regions. VERIFY 3D results showed that 83.20% of the structure residues have averaged 3D-1D score ≥ 0.1 . At least 80% of the amino acids have scored ≥ 0.1 in the 3D/1D profile. Obtained structure was

Chapter No. 5

aligned with the template, and a 1.38 Å RMSD value was obtained, which showed that the structure predicted is much similar and was built according to the template used.

AbL has a molecular weight of 50.064 kDa, and it contains a total of 520 amino acids having 2 domains that are connected via a double-stranded linker peptide. Each domain has a 20 Å radius and comprises 3 four-stranded β sheets and six helices. 26% of residues are found in β sheets, while 33% are found in helices. The antiparallel strand of one β sheet is constructed by the N and C termini, which are situated in domain I. The sequence of C-terminal part (residues 1–17 and 232–419) makes up the majority of domain I, whereas the N-terminal region makes up the majority of domain II (residues 22–227) (Schönbrunn *et al.*, 1996).

The process of virtual screening was done with the help of PyRx. This includes the selection of ligand. The ligand was selected from protein data bank PDB. All the ligands from that were selected. The screening results were observed, and the ligands with low binding free energies and RMSD values was selected. Ligand selected include the PubChem ID: GLU 753. It has RMSD value less than 2 Å. From 1.412 million chemicals in three databases (i.e., FDA-approved drugs, Sigma database, and ChemBridge database), putative Glycerol was found using a molecular docking-based virtual screening technique.

We have to obtain the *Agaricus bisporus* laccase 3D structure from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) or, in the absence of one, use homology modelling to predict the structure and remove any ions, water molecules, or other tiny molecules that aren't a part of the enzyme to prepare the protein structure. Assign atom kinds and include any extra atoms required for a full structure. Build the 3D structure of glycerol using molecular modelling tools or obtain it from chemical databases. Glycerol should be converted to the proper 3D structure format, such as PDB, SDF, or MOL2, and its shape should be optimised by reducing energy.

Select a reliable molecular docking programme for protein-ligand docking, such as AutoDock, AutoDock Vina, Glide, GOLD, or another popular programme. It is important to determine the location on *Agaricus bisporus* laccase's active site where glycerol is thought to bind. This can be accomplished using the catalytic location of the enzyme or any other structural data that is available. We have to create the docking parameters, which should

Chapter No. 5

include the search space (the area where Glycerol can attach), the number of docking poses to be produced, and any special requirements or preferences for the docking algorithm. Run the molecular docking simulation to determine the most advantageous Glycerol binding pose(s) within the enzyme's active site.

With each docking pose, the docking software produces a docking score that corresponds to the projected binding affinity. We examined the docking findings to determine the best docking pose(s) based on the interactions created between Glycerol and *Agaricus bisporus* laccase and the docking scores. We utilised molecular visualisation software to see the binding positions and examine the interactions between the enzyme and glycerol, such as hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions. It was done with great care when interpreting the data because molecular docking predictions aren't necessarily accurate depictions of actual binding interactions. Different methods were used like X-ray crystallography or other binding assays to do experimental validation to verify the expected binding mechanism and affinity between Glycerol and *Agaricus bisporus* laccase.

. In *Agaricus bisporus*, laccase predominantly contributes to the lignin breakdown and melanin synthesis processes, which are crucial for the mushroom's growth and development. *Agaricus bisporus* is a saprophytic fungus that breaks down complex organic matter to gain nutrients, however, it predominantly uses decaying plant matter and pollution degradation. Laccase plays an important role in the degradation of certain environmental pollutants particularly aromatic compounds. Effluents from numerous industrial activities often contain hazardous and resistant organic contaminants. Laccases can be utilised in bioremediation techniques to break down complex organic molecules into simpler and less hazardous chemicals, which can be used to cleanse toxic industrial effluents. Laccase can be used to treat organic waste, including municipal solid waste, agricultural waste, and waste from food production. Laccase can help lessen the negative effects of such waste on the environment by decomposing organic compounds.

CONCLUSION

Agaricus bisporus is one of the most widely cultivated edible mushrooms in the world. The chemical components of *A. bisporus* have a wide range of biological activities. In order to deeply understand the antioxidant properties of *A. bisporus*, this study conducted an investigation on the components of *A. bisporus* fermentation. (Wang and X. Chen. 2020).

Mushrooms are dried to increase the shelf life and make them easier to transport and store without refrigeration. UV-irradiated dried mushrooms are a good source of D vitamers. Vitamin D₂ and 25(OH)D₂ concentrations showed a gradual loss over 12 months, with the greatest rate of loss occurring during the latter 6 months. However, vacuum-sealed, UV-irradiated dried mushrooms kept at room temperature have a high retention of D-vitamers over 6 months after processing and packaging, a time span in which it is expected that most dried mushrooms would be cooked and consumed. Even after 12 months storage, UV-irradiated dried mushrooms still offered a valuable nutritional source of vitamin D₂ in a 20 g serving size. As vitamin D deficiency is prevalent throughout the world, UV-irradiated dried mushrooms provide an opportunity to provide a convenient, long shelf-life source of vitamin. (Jones SM, Solomon EI (2015)

Overall, the data discussed in this paper confirmed that insoluble, > 30 KDa MW fungoid KT can reduce the browning of model wines subjected to oxidation, with little differences between doses (0.5 or 1 g/L). The source of KT, whether from *Aspergillus niger* (AN) or *Agaricus bisporus* (AB), had only a marginal effect on the efficacy of the polymer, with AN formulations being slightly more effective, particularly at the highest dose. The role of oxidoreductive equilibrium of iron and its chelation by KT on the extent of Fenton reaction was highlighted. Water soluble oligomeric KT from *Agaricus bisporus*, on the other hand, was ineffective for that purpose, and the browning of those solutions was almost the same as the CTRL samples where no antioxidant was added. (Lam, S.S., X.Y. Lee, W.L. Nam)

In this study, the technology for preserving composite film packaging with a combination of OEO and slow-release nanoparticles was used to test the freshness of the mushrooms. The test results confirmed that the treatment combining OEO and MNS significantly delayed the deterioration in the quality of *A. bisporus* after 12 d of storage, thus maintaining their color, shape, fullness, and texture, thereby enhancing their commercial value. The OEO–MNS–TS film packaging reduced respiratory loss and microbial-induced

Chapter No. 6

spoilage of mushrooms, which reduced oxidative damage and retarding aging, thus extending the shelf life of the mushrooms and reducing packaging contamination. Therefore, this packaging treatment can be used effectively for composite preservation during postharvest storage and distribution of *A. bisporus* to prevent the quality degradation of mushrooms. The findings of this study provided a standard of reference for OEO and MNS application in packaging preservation.

In this study, three novel ACE inhibitory peptides were successfully obtained from scraps of *A. bisporus* using dual-enzyme hydrolysis. Under optimal process parameters, the extraction rate of ACE inhibitory peptides was 6.678% (calculated as mushroom protein). This provides a new path for the high-value utilisation of *A. bisporus* scraps. The average activity of the three novel ACE inhibitory peptides was 80.68%, and the IC₅₀ value was 0.9 mg/mL. The amino acid sequences of three novel ACE inhibitory peptides were LVYP and VYPW and YPWT. The stability verification results showed good tolerance to temperature, pH and gastrointestinal digestive enzymes, indicating good potential for the development of drugs for lowering blood pressure. Molecular docking revealed their binding mechanism, which provides guidance for the development of antihypertensive peptide drugs.

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Agarwal et al., 2016

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